

PROBLEMS OF INNOVATION MARKETING DEVELOPMENT IN TEXTILE AND SEWING-KNITTING ENTERPRISES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7004669>

Abstract. *In this article, the main directions of the strategy for the development of the market of sewing products, the formation of the innovative development strategy of the industrial products market, the formation of demand and supply and opportunities of the sewing products market, the preparation of new types of fabrics based on innovations, the adaptation of new production technologies to local raw materials are considered.*

Keywords: *enterprise, knitwear, innovation, technology, strategy, demand, supply.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО МАРКЕТИНГА В ТЕКСТИЛЬНЫХ И ШВЕЙНО-ТРИКОТАЖНЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены основные направления стратегии развития рынка швейной продукции, формирование стратегии инновационного развития рынка промышленной продукции, формирование спроса и предложения и возможности рынка швейной продукции, подготовка рассматриваются новые виды тканей на основе инноваций, адаптация новых технологий производства к местному сырью.*

Ключевые слова: *предприятие, трикотаж, инновации, технология, стратегия, спрос, предложение.*

INTRODUCTION

In the 1st quarter of 2021, 185,300 tons of cotton fibers were processed by textile enterprises (101% increase compared to last year). In addition, 150 enterprises produced 163.5 thousand tons of yarn in January-March this year (110.2% compared to last year).

Planned production and export processes by textile enterprises during the coronavirus pandemic. Various measures are being taken to ensure continuity and retention of employees.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2020 "On urgent measures to support the textile and sewing-knitting industry" provides a number of benefits and opportunities to enterprises.

Planned production and export processes by textile enterprises during the coronavirus pandemic. Various measures are being taken to ensure continuity and retention of employees.

Including;

- measures to ensure the health of workers, production workshops and sanitary safety of buildings and structures on the basis of a contract with regional health care and sanitary-epidemiological control;

- movement of motor vehicles in connection with the enterprise's production activities, regular disinfection and strict observance of sanitary and hygiene rules;

It is also planned to buy 123 thousand tons of cotton fibers and produce 113 thousand tons of yarn by textile enterprises in April-May of this year.

If we pay attention to the organizational structures of the innovative activities carried out in our country, at the modern stage, the innovation policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is

determined by the President and the Cabinet of Ministers and is implemented by a number of state administration bodies and local state authorities within their powers.

RESULTS

The legal and institutional changes aimed at the development of innovation policy in our country in recent years have caused further increase of the scientific and technical potential formed in the years of independence. In particular, it can be said that the Presidential Decree "On the establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was the main step in the implementation of administrative reforms for the wide introduction of innovative ideas, developments and technologies.

The strategy of innovative development of the market of light industrial products enables the economic assessment of the export potential of the industry based on the formation of the demand and supply and opportunities of the market of sewing products, the study of the domestic and foreign markets, and the formation of an information and advertising system. In our opinion, forecasting the supply and demand for network products, increasing the volume of processing of natural fibers, preparing new types of fabrics based on innovations, forming new production technologies based on adaptation to local raw materials should be among the main directions of the development strategy of the sewing products market. In the implementation of this strategy, the training of highly qualified personnel, their continuous training and retraining are of particular importance. Because no matter how good the ideas are,

The implementation of marketing research is of great importance in the innovative development of the light industry of our republic. By conducting such activities, it is possible to analyze the international market, research product sales markets, study marketing operations, collect and process information, research the marketing-mix complex, study competitors, benchmarking, demand and sales forecasting.

In the analytical function of marketing research, the factors of the external environment, the market, its elements and situation, consumers, the market, the product and the structure of the product, as well as the internal environment of the firm are analyzed. Factors controlled by the company's management - technological process, financial situation, organizational structure, market selection, etc. are taken into account. External environmental factors include uncontrollable factors such as consumers, competition, government, economy, technology, independent media.

The reduction of centralized planning bodies in the textile industry in a market economy requires independent movement in the formation and maintenance of branched and complex relationships. Accordingly, it is necessary to use the methods of market segmentation to produce effective plans for the development of the textile industry.

Market segmentation is the process of segmentation of consumers and sellers of textile products according to their demands and reactions in the market. The concept of marketing in the field of sales arises from the fact that sellers use a product in different ways and buy it for different motivations. It is necessary to move to maximal adaptation of the production and trade activities of the textile industry to the requirements of specific consumers. The main goal of consumer market segmentation is to group all consumers into one type of product as much as possible.

The segment of the consumer market must meet a number of requirements:

1. Each segment should be clearly described.
2. It is necessary to determine the specific requirements of consumers for each segment.
3. It is necessary to determine the specific characteristics of consumers.
4. The defined segment of consumers must be large enough to cover the costs of the product manufactured to satisfy consumer demand.
5. The segment must be suitable for the company to sell the product it produces

In our opinion, the main directions of the strategy of innovative development of the market of light industrial products should be:

1. Formation and development of light industrial machinery; re-equipment and modernization of existing enterprises; establishment of new high-tech enterprises.
2. Formation of demand and supply and possibilities of the market of light industrial products, study of domestic and foreign market, formation of information and advertising system, economic assessment of export potential, forecasting of supply and demand for industry products.
3. Increasing processing of natural fibers, preparation of new types of fibers based on innovations, formation of new production technologies based on adaptation to local raw materials.
4. Creation of new jobs based on the training of highly qualified personnel, continuous training and retraining, expansion and re-formation of branch enterprises.

DISCUSSION

The importance of marketing research in the organization, management, planning and control of overall marketing activities is shown as one of the main features of modern marketing theory. High-level organization of marketing research is the initial stage, i.e., the "base point" in determining and implementing the marketing strategy of enterprises and organizations, the set of methods used in their scope, analytical and processing processes. In today's environment, where the consumer market is increasingly enriched with new goods and services, the importance of marketing research in identifying new opportunities and using them wisely is increasing day by day.

Consumers-buyers can purchase all types of goods and resources produced in the community. Therefore, the total size of the social product, including the preparation of the means of production, is the main determining factor of marketing.

In the innovative development of the light industry of our republic, marketing research can be carried out in five major directions:

- firstly, by carrying out advertising research, that is, to inspire buyers, advertising tests, types of advertising and their comparative effectiveness;
- secondly, through strategic planning and organizational policy, that is, making short- and long-term predictions, analysis of enterprise results and market opportunities, new diversification development opportunities, analysis of operational gross and internal environment of the organization, as well as export market observations;
- thirdly, by conducting research on the responsibility of the organization, that is, increasing the social responsibility of the organization in terms of customer formation and environmental protection;

- fourthly, to analyze the market, that is, to carry out work on the attitude of buyers to new goods, potential and opportunities of new goods, testing of new goods, problems of packaging of goods and its inspection;

- fifthly, researching sales opportunities, conducting marketing research, i.e. identifying potential or potential markets, analyzing market structure, sales volume changes, conducting test marketing, conducting sales promotion studies.

Of course, each organization carries out marketing research in one direction or another according to its capabilities and goals. It takes into account the organization's strategy for a certain period, required tactical actions. A company's goal is usually expressed in the form of financial indicators, and these indicators give an idea of what the company wants to achieve over a certain period of time, for example, one year, two years, and five years.

In our opinion, there are other motivating factors of an economic nature to attract investments in the light industrial sector. These are, first of all: the presence of huge resources of raw materials, mainly high-quality cotton fiber; low cost of the energy network; availability of qualified and relatively inexpensive labor resources; developed network of communication; banking and legal branches of services; such as the presence of large and untapped markets selling ready-made textile products in the region (the population of Central Asian countries is more than 55 million people) and wool and semi-finished products in the European Union countries.

Along with the analysis of external factors, the planning process in innovative marketing requires the study of the enterprise, that is, the internal analysis. By studying the enterprise, it should answer the questions of whether the level of training of sales managers meets the requirements, the condition of the equipment, and whether the quality of our goods is satisfactory compared to that of competitors.

CONCLUSIONS

In our republic today, there are serious obstacles in the use of innovative marketing technologies and tools, which can be divided into problems related to organizational and human resources.

As organizational problems:

- although the legal basis of the system of support of innovative organizations has been formed, its actual application is not at the required level;

- the implementation of innovative ideas in large production and service enterprises is relatively late and requires a lot of time;

- it can be shown that the lack of competitive environment in the market of new technologies leads to a decrease in the demand for selling innovative products.

Factors such as technological advantages of the product, compatibility with the company's capabilities, and the use of evaluation processes in the selection of new models are also important in the effective implementation of innovative marketing work in the company.

Although the support of new products by the management of the enterprise and the existence of a competitive environment are in the lower places in the group of success factors, they are considered as a component of the production factors of innovative products.

REFERENCES

1. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Further improvement of management in light industry in 2017-2021, intensive development and diversification measures". February 13, 2017, PQ-2772.
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 5, 2020 No. PF-5989 "On urgent measures to support the textile and sewing-knitting industry"
3. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kasimova MS, Ergashkhodjaeva Sh.J. Strategic marketing. Study guide. 2010.-161 p.
4. Bekmurodov A.Sh., Kasimova MS Safarov BJ, Musayeva Sh. Marketing management. Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2007, p. 160.
5. Fattokhov AA, RNKarimova distributor activities in the market. Study guide. - T.: TDIU, 2009.-227b.
6. Kasimova MS, Abduhalilova LT Marketing studies. - T.: TDIU, 2010.-157 p.
7. Kasimova MS, Samadov AN, Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.J. Economics of commercial enterprises. - T.: TDIU, 2010.163 p.
8. Korotkov T.L. Commercialization and marketing innovation: monograph M.: Kreativnaya ekonomika, 2012. 168 p.
9. Peter F. Drucker. The Practice of Management, 1954 / Cit. po: Kumar, N. Marketing kak strategy /N. Kumar. M.: Pretext, 2008. 342 p.
10. Permichev N. F., Paleeva O. A.. Marketing innovative: uchebnoe posobie. N. Novgorod: Nizhegorod.gos. archit.-stroit. un-t, 2011.
11. Perchinskaya, O. The evolution in innovation theory and its influence on art-business. 233-236 p
12. Korotkov, T., Vlasov, A. Innovative role in marketing and commercialization. In: Practical marketing, no. 3, 2014.
13. Kiselev, V. Degtyareva. Strategic factors of successful marketing innovation //Marketing, no. 5, 2013.
14. Aaker D., i dr. Marketingovy issledovaniya. Izd. 7-e. Per. s English / Pod ed. S. Bojuk. - SPb.: Peter, 2004, - 848 p.
15. Basovsky L.E. Marketing: Course lecture. - M.: INFRA-M, 2010. - 219 p.
16. Bronnikova T.S. Marketing: theory, practice: uchebnoe posobie / T.S. Bronnikova - 2nd ed., pererab. i dop. - M.: KNORUS, 2010. - 208 p.
17. Golubkov E.P. Basic marketing. 2-e pererab. i dop. - M.: Finpress, 2003. - 688 p.
18. Grigorev M.N. Marketing. - M.: Gardariki, 2006, - 366 p.
19. Zavyalov P.S. Marketing and schemes, drawings, tables: Uchebnoe posobie. - M.: INFRA-M, 2006, - 496 p.
20. Ibragimov R.G. Marketing. Darslik, T.: "Sharq", 2002
21. Kalka Regine. Marketing / Regine Kalka, Andrea Messen; (per. s German. M.V. Lapshinova). – 3rd ed., ster. - M.: SmartBuk, 2010. - 126 p.: il.
22. Karpova S.V. International marketing for university students / S.V. Karpova. - Rostov n/d: Phoenix, 2010. - 184 p.